

The LoGoTRI-Philnet Portal for Local Governance

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the LoGo-TRI or “Local Government training and research institute Philippine network” Portal, which is an online platform that can be tapped by LGUs for development programs to enhance technical and conceptual capacities, as well as competencies of LGUs. In evaluating the effectiveness and capacity of a local government unit, what is needed is a sought-after Seal of Good and Local Governance – an award, incentive, and honor recognition-based program for all LGUs. In the latest audit of 1,706 LGUs, only 380 passed as ALL-IN. The objective is to create an accessible online platform using the LoGo-TRI network, for capacity building purposes for all LGUs in the Philippines. Major findings in a study conducted by McKay et al. (2012), states that using IT governance motivates disinterested officials and energizes management sectors; Davila & Bollinger 2012 also conducted a study evaluating the effectiveness of online training implemented at a government agency in Thailand. This study developed an online network to provide training to its employees across the country, and examined the program’s instructional effectiveness by measuring trainees’ performance on pre and post-tests, satisfaction, and motivation. Results indicate significant increases in trainees’ test scores. Based on the research, creation of an online platform is the best solution that will integrate and display all available services that can address the segments crafted by the interagency technical working group. This has been determined as the optimal solution to break the barrier of all LGUs in the country.

KEYWORDS

LoGo-TRI, LGUs, SGLG,

1 INTRODUCTION

It is a fact that the Philippines continues to face economic crisis, disasters, political issues and the impact of climate change. Thus, there is a continuing demand for government services as mandated by law, particularly at the local level of governance. To face these challenges, workforce reshaping as well as training and skills development among government units are needed. However, resources for skills training are scarce and usually limited. Investments in these programs are not frequently prioritized, and evaluating outcomes is considered challenging in many aspects. This paper presents the LoGo-TRI or “Local Government training and research institute Philippine network” Portal, which is an online platform that can be tapped by LGUs for development programs to enhance technical and conceptual capacities, as well as competencies of LGUs.

In evaluating the effectiveness and capacity of a local government unit, what is needed is a sought-after Seal of Good and Local Governance – which is an award, incentive, and honor recognition-based program for all LGUs. It serves

as a stark reminder to LGUs to fulfill their duties as well as welcome progress that equates to upgrading in performance and services. After years of execution, the SGLG MC was enacted as Republic Act 11292 dated July 23, 2018 – An Act Establishing and Institutionalizing the Seal of Good Local Governance for Local Government Units, and allocating for this purpose the Seal of Good Local Governance Fund. After its formalization, the SGLG updates the assessment criteria from “4+1” to “ALL-IN”, requiring that the LGU must pass all areas of: (1) Financial Administration; (2) Disaster Preparedness; (3) Social Protection; (4) Peace and Order; (5) Business-Friendliness and Competitiveness; (6) Environmental Management; (7) Tourism, Culture and the Arts. Based on the Philippine Statistics Authority, there are 1,715 LGUs in the country. In the latest audit of 1,706 entities consisting of 81 provinces, 145 cities and 1,480 municipalities, only 380 passed as ALL-IN in the SGLG Audit, out of all the assessed LGUs.

The result of the SGLG Audit showed 380 LGUs passed out of 1,715; it has been shown that there are constraints in the availability of training resources, lack of investments coming in for these programs, as well as hindrances in producing accurate outcome evaluations. Based on the result of the assessment, DILG together with the interagency technical working group saw the need of capacitating the LGUs by way of a variety of dialogues, networking, and the presence of the academe for further education to improve the LGUs capacity for improvements in the delivery of services. This study aims to present an online platform (The LoGo TRI- Philnet Portal) to be used by LGUs for government leadership, skills and development programs and examination of training impacts that can be used for the betterment of the government unit, preparation for their workforce, and to handle future challenges.

2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Philippines as a third world country faces a multitude of adversities in local agencies. Based on the data provided in the audit, Philippine LGUs lack preparedness and modernization. This study aims to create an accessible network for the LGUs training and development.

3 GENERAL OBJECTIVE

To create an accessible online platform using the LoGo-TRI network for capacity building for all LGUs in the Philippines.

3.1 Specific Objectives

- To standardize the LoGo-TRI Network to be accessible to LGUs anywhere and anytime throughout the Philippines.

- To enable the website to be a standard tool for the 1,715 LGUs to secure the Seal of Good and Local Governance and its corresponding accreditation criteria.
- To provide a website with easy access thru online learning for training and development.
- To create a user-friendly platform to educate and train LGU officials such as Mayors, Barangay officials, councilors, governors, board members and other LGU staff members throughout the country.

4 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The government relies on the capacity of every government official to acquire and possess skills and training in maintaining their competency and role in society. This heavily relies on continuous employee reskilling. This paper aims to present the The LoGo-TRI “Local Government training and research institute Philippine network” Portal as an online platform for LGUs in developing technical and intangible capacities, as well as their respective aptitudes. This paper outlines the significance to facilitate an effective network using a website as a tool to equip all local government unit personnel with enhanced, credible competencies, solid outcomes, and work-related improvements. A web-based network also addresses the needs of organizations seeking to become more competitive by building a well-trained, skills-enhanced workforce.

A study conducted by McKay et al. (2012), states that using information technology governance motivates disinterested officials and energizes management sectors. It was cited by the authors that their study highlighted desirable change, improved efficiencies, and efficacy in training resources. This study has evolved through effective Web 2.0 tools as an emergent self-designing eLearning system that caters towards Web based participants. The study concluded that content and quality of an online training network is dependent on its design with utmost consideration and priority to become a flexible, user-centered, adaptive web-based training program. This is accomplished by employing the integrated power of Web 2.0 tools that will improve the delivery of information to the users. A user-centric, easy-to-use and adaptive online network relies heavily on a well-thought of design interface. A poor example of an interface leads to users requiring more time in learning the instructional materials rather than mastering the knowledge and data provided in the network (Ardito et al., 2006).

Davila & Bollinger 2012 conducted a study evaluating the effectiveness of online training implemented at a government agency in Thailand. This study developed an online network to provide training to its employees across the country. This study aimed to examine the program’s instructional effectiveness by measuring trainees’ performance on pre and post-tests, satisfaction, and motivation. Results from this indicate significant increases in trainees’ test scores. Overall, trainees were moderately motivated and satisfied with courses delivered in both systems. A statistically significant relationship between satisfaction and motivation in the online training environment was found. This literature strongly suggests the

effectiveness of an online network that can be used for training and development programs.

5 DISCUSSION

With self-governance and independence as the main challenges of the country, the Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) was developed as the principal government office assigned to undertake a variety of functions ranging from supervision over local units, public instructions, control and supervision over local agencies, counter-insurgency, rehabilitation, community development and development programs for cooperatives. Confronted by these challenges, the LGUs supervised by DILG need to avail of and undergo enhanced training, standardization on capacity building and skills development.

Assessing the effectiveness and capacity of a local government unit, the Seal of Good and Local Governance (SGLG) is sought after by LGUs for accreditation. The SGLG is accredited to LGUs by the council headed by DILG. The council is composed of the following: Department of Interior and Local Government (DILG); Department of Budget and Management (DBM); Department of Finance (DOF); Department of Health (DOH); Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD); Department of Tourism (DOT); Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR); National Economic and Development Authority (NEDA); Department of National Defense (DND) and the National Anti-Poverty Commission (NAPC).

However, given that the government cannot provide all the technical knowledge needed to capacitate these LGUs, there will be a need for other partners to intervene to achieve these segments. This study presents the network that will also cover dialogues, knowledge exchange, and organizational development support, creation of a network that will form a pool of trainers, on-the-job coaching and the like. The LoGoTRI-PhilNet was formed by the Local Government Academy last 2003 to provide capacity-building interventions and services to the local government. It is a non-stock, non-profit national association of local resource institutions (LRIs) that provides capacity-building interventions and services to the local government.

These are the proposed approaches in the network: Dialogue - that will open knowledge exchange and organizational development support; Network - creation of a network that will produce trainers who will, in turn, produce and train future trainers; Academe - Presence of partner academic institutions that will cater to continuing education, study visits and the like; On duty - This highlights on-the-job coaching and/or face-to-face training sessions.

At present, these are how LGUs access the network: State Universities and Colleges (SUC’s) extension program Every educational institution includes its own extension program/s as one of the integral parts of their setup and offerings regarding social responsibility. However, in the case of SUCs with grant programs, these are not all-inclusive and does not cover and benefit all LGUs. Only select number

of LGUs will have the opportunity for involvement and collaboration in the University's program.

DILG-LGRC (DILG – Local Government Resource Center) Interface of regional DILG-LGRC, SUCs and LGUs is an annual occurrence, of which the same parties on a yearly basis also do assessment. However, the same circumstances arise in which not all LGUs have the capabilities and capacity to join and to be involved in all of the projects, most especially if your LGU is not part or included in the chosen and preferred targeted area/s. This is the current state as per DILG's training arm.

Intervention of Local and International Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs and INGOs)

Due to the needs and demands in the event of a calamity or a catastrophic event, NGOs like Save the Children, United Nations, Red Cross, are offering their support in whatever way they can to the government by providing aid in times of dire need. The problem in this case is that not all LGUs are given the opportunity to be a target beneficiary or qualify as such, implying that this is on a need basis. An example is what would qualify as an urgent need by an LGU, such as Tacloban, which was hit and devastated by a Storm Surge/Tsunami. Given the destruction, magnitude, and severity of casualties, as well as the damage to the local economy and infrastructure during such a catastrophic event, there is a necessity to allocate and expedite special funding which is not only allotted to the concerned LGU by the government, but by all active and participating international and local NGOs. The selection can become extremely specific in which the criteria fits identified and affected LGUs only.

According to Dr. Era (President of the Network), their present condition has a wide network coverage located in parts all over the country, and possible activities that they can offer are online forums, MOOCs, and distance learning, which all require corresponding technology. This paper aims to showcase the capacity of the LoGo-TRI Network, whose overall aim is to be accessible by LGUs anytime, anywhere around the Philippines.

6 CONCLUSION

Appropriate capacity building interventions like trainings and education are unavailable in their specific jurisdiction. Hence, the Department of the Interior and Local Government through its attached agency, the Local Government Academy as the training arm of the Department, have formed a network composed of Philippine State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) and other of institutions who share the same goal to serve as resource institutions to provide expertise and venues for formal training and higher education.

Given the current times, government funds are being used to address the country's urgent concerns – travel, capacity enhancement activities, training and development were put on hold to focus on matters that are considered highly urgent. The ideal and primary solution is the use of modern information and technology to assist personnel in assessing their capabilities and search for the most appropriate training and/or education that they will need.

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